

ISSN (o): 3030-3362

N^o 3(12)

27.03.2024

RESEARCH AND IMPLEMENTATION
TADQIQ VA TATBIQ
ILMIY-USLUBIY JURNALI

CERTIFICATE
N^o 078777

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Jurnal oyda bir
marta nashr etiladi.

Nashr tillari:

O'zbek, rus, ingliz va
qoraqalpoq

O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Prezidenti Administratsiyasi
huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy
kommunikatsiya agentligida
2023-yil 3-mayda
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HYPERCORTICISM AND ACROMEGALY KEY PATHOLOGIES OF VITAMIN D METABOLISM DISORDERS

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Annotation. *Due to the continued high prevalence of low levels of vitamin D in the blood of people in the vast majority of regions of the world, the discovery of the variety of extraskeletal effects of vitamin D, the issue of maintaining adequate intake of vitamin D in the body remains extremely urgent, especially in individuals at risk of severe deficiency. Few studies have been conducted on the peculiarities of vitamin D metabolism in pathological conditions such as hypercortisolism and acromegaly. However, vitamin D deficiency in such patients may occur more often and be more pronounced than in the general population. For the treatment of most of these diseases, it is now recommended to use standard prophylactic and therapeutic doses of vitamin D for the general population, which may not meet the therapeutic goals specific to each disease. This review provides information about the metabolism of vitamin D under normal conditions, and also reviews literature data concerning the study of the possible connection and mutual influence of these endocrinopathies and the metabolism of vitamin D.*

Keywords: *vitamin D, vitamin D deficiency, hypercortisolism, acromegaly.*

ГИПЕРКОРТИЦИЗМ И АКРОМЕГАЛИЯ – КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ ПАТОЛОГИИ НАРУШЕНИЯ ОБМЕНА ВИТАМИНА D

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Аннотация. В связи с сохраняющейся высокой распространенностью низкого уровня витамина D в крови людей в подавляющем большинстве регионов мира, открытием разнообразия внескелетных эффектов витамина D, остро стоит вопрос поддержания адекватного поступления витамина D в организм человека. организме остается чрезвычайно актуальным, особенно у людей, подверженных риску серьезного дефицита. Исследования особенностей метаболизма витамина D при таких патологических состояниях, как гиперкортицизм и акромегалия, проведены мало. Однако дефицит витамина D у таких пациентов может встречаться чаще и быть более выраженным, чем в общей популяции. Для лечения большинства этих заболеваний в настоящее время рекомендуется использовать стандартные профилактические и терапевтические дозы витамина D для населения в целом, которые могут не соответствовать терапевтическим целям, специфичным для каждого заболевания. В обзоре представлены сведения о метаболизме витамина D в норме, а также рассмотрены литературные данные, касающиеся изучения возможной связи и взаимного влияния этих эндокринопатий и метаболизма витамина D.

Ключевые слова: витамин D, дефицит витамина D, гиперкортицизм, акромегалия.

Introduction. Significant progress has been made to date in the fight against rickets, the most severe consequence of vitamin D deficiency. However, the prevalence of low vitamin D levels, which predisposes to osteopenia, osteomalacia, muscle weakness and an increased risk of fractures, remains high in the vast majority of regions of the world. In addition, the discovery of the ubiquitous expression of the vitamin D receptor and the paracrine secretion of the active form of vitamin D (1,25(OH)₂D) in body tissues led to intensive study of the extraskelatal effects of vitamin D and led to the formation of new views on its physiological role. In this regard, the issue of maintaining adequate levels of vitamin D, especially in individuals with risk factors for severe deficiency [1]. Sources of vitamin D and the main stages of its metabolism

Vitamin D enters the human body as a result of exposure to ultraviolet radiation on the skin, with food and nutritional supplements. Food sources of vitamin D include primarily fatty fish, as well as mushrooms and egg yolks. In some countries, food products are fortified with vitamin D (breakfast cereals, dairy products, orange juice, etc.). Under the influence of ultraviolet radiation of the spectrum B (wavelength 290–315 nm), previtamin D₃ is formed from 7-dehydrocholesterol in the skin, which is quickly isomerized into D₃ (colecalciferol). Both vitamin D₂ (ergocalciferol, formed in mushrooms from ergosterol under the influence of ultraviolet radiation) and D₃ (colecalciferol) can come from food and dietary supplements; these two forms, due to identical subsequent metabolism, are often referred to together as "D". Vitamin D, which comes from food and dietary supplements, and is also synthesized in the skin, undergoes 2 stages of hydroxylation to acquire biological activity: in the first stage, as a result of 25-hydroxylation by the enzyme CYP2R1 in the liver, 25-hydroxyvitamin D (25(OH)D) is formed - the main circulating form of vitamin D, which is used to assess the sufficiency of vitamin D status. Subsequently, 25(OH)D is hydroxylated at the 1 α position by the enzyme CYP27B1, resulting in the formation of 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D (1,25(OH)₂D) – a form that can bind to the vitamin D receptor (VDR) and realizes the biological effects of vitamin D. The main source of circulating 1,25(OH)₂D is the kidneys. The enzyme CYP24A1 (24-hydroxylase) catabolizes both 25(OH)D and 1,25(OH)₂D into biologically inactive forms [2, 3]. Unlike 25(OH)D, the concentration of which is relatively stable, the synthesis of 1,25(OH)₂D is tightly regulated: PTH stimulates 1 α -hydroxylase, while FGF-23 and 1,25(OH)₂D itself due to negative feedback connections reduce its activity. Changes in the concentration of calcium and phosphorus in the blood serum, including due to changes in their concentration in food, can have an indirect effect on the activity of 1 α -hydroxylase. It is assumed that the process 24-hydroxylation is regulated reciprocally by 1 α -hydroxylation. Since VDR is a nuclear transcription factor, the high abundance of vitamin D-responsive DNA elements in the genome determines the variety of effects of vitamin D described to date on both bone metabolism and calcium-phosphorus metabolism, and on other physiological processes. The classic effects of vitamin D through 1,25(OH)₂D include

primarily enhancing absorption of calcium in the small intestine by increasing the expression in the epithelium of the apical membrane calcium channel (TRPV6), a cytoplasmic calcium transporter (calbindin-D9K calcium-binding protein) and basolateral membrane calcium pump (PMCA1b). There is also evidence that 1,25(OH)₂D can increase intercellular calcium absorption observed with high dietary calcium intake. According to some data, 1,25(OH)₂D is able to influence phosphorus absorption by increasing the transcription of intestinal sodium-phosphorus co-transporter IIb, but it is assumed that the main factor determining absorption of phosphorus in the intestine is the concentration of phosphorus in food [4]. To date, only a few studies have been carried out on the characteristics of vitamin D metabolism in pathological conditions such as hypercortisolism and acromegaly. However, vitamin D deficiency in such patients, according to available literature data, may occur more often and be more pronounced than in the general population. This review summarizes the available data on the characteristics of vitamin D metabolism in hypercortisolism and acromegaly. Vitamin D and hypercortisolism. Data from early studies on the effect of excess glucocorticoids on vitamin D metabolism are very contradictory, due to the high heterogeneity of the study groups. In 1986, Kugai et al. showed that among individuals with Cushing's syndrome and severe osteopenia, higher concentrations of 1,25(OH)₂D were observed compared with patients without osteopenia and the control group; this was explained by increased calciuria, which caused an increase in PTH and, accordingly, the synthesis of 1,25(OH)₂D [5]. A slight increase in 1,25(OH)₂D concentration without a change in 25(OH)D content was shown by Hahn et al. in healthy adults after a short course of prednisolone (20 mg/day for 2 weeks), while intestinal calcium absorption decreased, due to which led to the conclusion that the decrease in intestinal calcium absorption caused by glucocorticosteroids cannot be attributed to a decrease circulating concentrations of the main known vitamin D metabolites [6]. In a study by Findling et al. the concentration of 25(OH)D and 1,25(OH)₂D in patients with ACTH-dependent hypercortisolism (Cushing's disease and ACTH-ectopia) before treatment did not differ from that in persons without the disease from the control group (17±6 ng/ml and 44±19 pg/ml, and 24±18 ng/ml and 37±10 pg/ml, respectively), however, after surgical treatment, the concentration of 25(OH)D did not change, and 1,25(OH)₂D fell, in on average, from 44 to 22 pg/ml (p<0.02); in addition, the concentration of PTH, normal before treatment, significantly decreased, tubular reabsorption of phosphate and the concentration of serum phosphorus increased, and urinary calcium excretion decreased [7]. Since the researchers did not find a correlation between PTH concentrations and 1,25(OH)₂D, a glucocorticoid-mediated increase in 1,25(OH)₂D concentrations was assumed; The researchers also do not exclude the influence of changes in phosphorus homeostasis on the results obtained (low dietary phosphate intake may increase the concentration of 1,25(OH)₂D independently of PTH). A glucocorticosteroid-mediated change in the rate of 1,25(OH)₂D inactivation could explain these results, but Seeman

et al. showed a small but significant decrease in the concentrations of 25(OH)D and 1,25(OH)₂D and no the effect of changing the rate of degradation of 1,25(OH)₂D [8]. The work of Corbee et al. Identical concentration values of 25(OH)D and 1,25(OH)₂D were observed in dogs with central hypercortisolism before and after removal of the pituitary gland, as well as when compared with the control group [9]. Similar results were obtained by Jiang et al. after administering high doses of dexamethasone to rats [10]. In the work of Klein et al. a decrease in 25(OH)D concentration in conditions of excess glucocorticoids was shown in a dose-dependent manner [11]. Subsequently, disturbances in calcium-phosphorus homeostasis became a systematic finding in patients exposed to excess glucocorticoids. It has become known that under the influence of glucocorticoids the complex process of calcium absorption in the duodenum is disrupted. Huybers et al. found that oral administration of 10 mg/kg prednisolone to 12-week-old mice on a regular diet decreased the intestinal calcium absorption capacity by halving duodenal TRPV6 mRNA expression and calbindin-D9K expression [12]. These effects could not be reproduced in other in vivo models, which was likely due to the chosen dose of glucocorticoids and the age of the experimental animals [13]. In addition, glucocorticoids also inhibit renal tubular reabsorption of calcium, promoting renal calcium loss and resulting negative calcium balance. In addition to these effects on calcium metabolism, glucocorticoids cause phosphaturia and reduce tubular phosphate reabsorption by inhibiting tubular expression of the sodium gradient-dependent phosphate transporter [14, 15]. In later studies, it was demonstrated that the development of disturbances in calcium-phosphorus metabolism in hypercortisolism may be contributed by the direct influence of glucocorticoids on the metabolism and implementation of the effects of vitamin D. Thus, in experimental studies, dexamethasone increased the renal expression of 24-hydroxylase [16, 17], and when prednisolone was prescribed, 25-hydroxylase activity was inhibited [18]. Functional cooperation has been noted between the glucocorticoid receptor, the transcription factor C/EBP β and the vitamin D receptor, increasing the transcription of 24-hydroxylase [19]. Interestingly, with dexamethasone treatment, vitamin D receptor mRNA levels in the kidney and duodenum increased significantly during the first day but decreased by the fifth day; these data, in turn, may explain the previously described changes in the transcription of duodenal and renal calbindin-D9K, TRPV5 and TRPV6 [20]. Thus, experimental data allow us to formulate the concept that with an excess of glucocorticoids, vitamin D deficiency develops due to accelerated catabolism of 25(OH)D. The clinical data available to date cannot convincingly support this hypothesis, but it should be remembered that the study groups are highly heterogeneous: the obesity observed in hypercortisolism, as well as other characteristics of patients exposed to excess glucocorticoids, such as, may contribute to the development of vitamin D deficiency. photosensitivity in systemic lupus erythematosus or limited physical activity in rheumatoid arthritis. A meta-analysis of studies published between

1970 and 2011 that did not include studies in patients receiving at least 400 IU of vitamin D per day. with a duration of glucocorticosteroid therapy of less than 2 weeks, with liver or kidney disease in more than 50% of patients, or after transplantation in patients with Cushing's syndrome, showed that the average concentration of 25(OH)D in patients receiving glucocorticosteroid therapy corresponded to suboptimal values (22.4 ng/ml) and was statistically significantly lower than in healthy controls, but did not differ from that in patients not receiving steroid drugs with an active form of the disease [21]. Taking into account the obtained average concentration of 25(OH). The authors calculated that to achieve a 25(OH)D concentration of at least 32 ng/ml in patients, 1800 IU of colecalciferol per day would be required. The International Endocrine Society guidelines recommend higher doses for individuals receiving corticosteroid therapy (3000–6000 IU per day) [22], whereas the American College of Rheumatology guidelines suggest significantly lower doses: 800–1000 IU per day in the 2010 revision [23].], and even lower – in the 2017 revision (600–800 IU per day) [24]. In the work of Ortego-Jurado et al. compared the concentration of 25(OH)D in patients with autoimmune diseases receiving long-term glucocorticosteroid therapy, additionally taking colecalciferol 800 IU per day or calcidiol at a dose of 354 IU per day. In addition to the fact that a negative correlation was found between the concentration of 25(OH)D and the dose of glucocorticosteroids taken, as well as body mass index, in the group of persons receiving calcidiol, consistently higher concentrations of 25(OH)D were observed regardless of the season (average 35.0 ng/ml and 24.6 ng/ml, respectively). The authors noted that the dose of colecalciferol was insufficient to maintain optimal vitamin D concentrations [25].

Conclusion. Available literature data indicate the presence of complex connections between hypercortisolism and acromegaly and vitamin D metabolism. It is not possible to formulate a clear concept characterizing these relationships, since there are significant contradictions between the results of experimental and clinical studies. Since determining the optimal vitamin D status and how to achieve it in these pathologies can help expand therapeutic options, research is required additional studies to obtain a more accurate characterization of the observed pathophysiological processes.

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научно-методический журнал

Том 02. | Вып. 03. | 2024

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ISSN 3030-3362.

Jurnal aniq va tabiiy fanlar, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy fanlar, texnika fanlari, tibbiyot fanlari, pedagogika fanlari sohalarini qamrab oladi. Tahrir hay‘ati a‘zolidan respublikaning turli OTMlarida faoliyat olib boruvchi fan nomzodlari va doktorlari o‘rin olishgan..

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Научно-методический журнал “ Исследования и внедрение ”

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Учредителем научно-технического журнала

«Исследования и внедрение» является ООО “Fer-Teach”.

Журнал издается с 2023 года, зарегистрирован 3 мая 2023 года Агентством информации и массовых коммуникаций при Администрации Президента Республики Узбекистан (Сертификат № 078777).

ISSN 3030-3362.

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ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal

Tom 02. | Son. 03. | 2024

Research and implementation
scientific-methodical journal

Vol. 02. | Iss. 03. | 2024

Исследования и внедрение
научно-методический журнал

Том 02. | Вып. 03. | 2024

Scientific and methodological journal “Research and implementation”

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The scientific and methodological journal “Research and implementation” was founded by Fer-Teach LLC and supported by the Fergana branch of the Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khorezmi. This journal was registered by the Agency of Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on May 3, 2023 (No 078777).

ISSN 3030-3362.

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